

METHODOLOGY OF USING MODERN METHODS AND TOOLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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Abstract: The importance of English in the modern world is incomparable. This is the most common language. More than 450 million people speak it as their mother tongue. Another 600-650 million citizens use English as an additional language for communication. It meets the demand in many countries of the world. Vocabulary and grammar aspects of this language are necessary for studying abroad. Without doing this, you want to be respected and highly paid. In this article, you can learn all the features of the English language, as well as why it is required.

Keywords: knowledge, foundation, performance, participation, well-paid work, related, including speaking, reading, writing, listening, motivation, opportunity, performance, learning title, emphasized, approach, knowledgeable, language learning, role playing, attribute, status, foreign country, technology, modern, information, communication.

In today's rapidly developing age, science and technology are growing rapidly. Progress in every field is taking a step forward. Hu Susan, great changes and significant progress are being made in science. Delivery of each subject to students using new innovative pedagogical technologies is one of the main requirements of today's education. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, writing, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It is also intended to increase the quality and effectiveness of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are several advantages of using such information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language. The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is important. The use of technological tools is necessary in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, reading, listening and speaking). In order to listen and understand the problems, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, and CD discs.

Listening comprehension is one of the most important components of

language learning. At the same time, the student is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, compliance with grammatical rules, vocabulary and meaning. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in the educational process is that students know and use information and communication technologies well. Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technology is one of the most fruitful ways. In this process, including: - when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues and cartoons; - it is possible to listen and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs; - the use of tape recorders and cassettes, which are considered a more traditional method; - CD players can be used. The use of these technical tools makes the process of foreign language learning more interesting and effective for students. In the process of globalization, it is difficult to imagine our life without the Internet. It is one of the most effective ways to use it effectively in the process of learning and teaching a foreign language. You will have the opportunity to communicate with people who speak foreign languages through the Internet. You can improve writing practice by writing letters via e-mail. Bringing modern communication technologies into the educational process, using them purposefully and correctly, and using them to increase the student's interest in a foreign language and increase the effectiveness of teaching is the most important issue.

Through this, the opportunity to use innovative technologies of education will be created and the demand will increase. Today, there are several different methods of innovative educational technologies. If they use wide and different methods to cover the topic in the classroom, the efficiency of the lesson will be high and the increase of students' interest in the lesson will be ensured. It is intended to increase the effectiveness of education by introducing innovations into the educational process and implementing them. The use of various role-playing and action games in the teaching of foreign language classes increases the interest in the lesson and language learning. By having students work in pairs or small groups, it helps students communicate with others. The use of graphic organizers in the educational process is one of the most important ways to explain the topic and convey the message to students.

It is also possible to use several different graphic organizers to cover the same topic. When teaching a foreign language, it is appropriate to use graphic organizers to explain new words and grammatical rules related to the topic. It will also be easy to remember if these are presented through graphic organizers.

The effectiveness of using different tables in the process of teaching a foreign language is also high. Using tables in the educational process, students can learn a certain grammar rule, problems, and use them to make sentences and insert new words. At a time when the need to learn a foreign language is high, effective use of modern information technologies and innovative educational technologies in the educational process will make this process effective. The effectiveness of innovative educational technologies is when they are used correctly and effectively in the educational process.

Interfaol is an English word, "interact": "inter" - mutual and "act" - to act), and when they are summarized, "Interfaol" means to act mutually. "Interaction" means cooperation (with others). That is, interactive methods of learning are a special form of organizing knowledge and communicative activity, in which students are involved in the learning process, they have the opportunity to understand and think about what they know and think. . The interactive method is to increase the effectiveness of the lesson due to the interaction between the teacher and students, to learn a new lesson through the teacher's independent action, reflection, discussion, and to independently achieve the set goal. , trying to find answers in microgroups, that is, the student thinks, writes, speaks, listens, most importantly, actively participates. Interactive teaching methods are especially effective in practical training. When using interactive teaching methods, the teacher's task consists of organizing group work and managing microgroup leaders (i.e. conducting). learns, the student learns. We have to learn a new role as teachers. To provide modern knowledge, the teacher himself must have such knowledge. Which of the interactive methods should be included and to what extent? It depends on the skill of the teacher.

Naturally, the teacher who uses this method in such children should take into account the level of knowledge of the students and what they are capable of and unable to do. The organization of the lesson in an interactive way means that only the student should think, think, act, leaving everything to the student may not have a good effect, the teacher should also stimulate the student's thoughts and encourage them to be active. The main task of the teacher in the pedagogical process is management. It controls the process of formation, development, education and upbringing of a person. Management is directing, assigning tasks, teaching, helping, supporting, advising, leading, observing, demanding and giving instructions. For active teaching, the teacher must: It is necessary to pay attention to: More use of non-traditional forms of lessons, including new pedagogical technologies and interactive methods:

- a) competition lessons;
- b) discussion classes;
- c) conferees;
- d) traveling companions;
- e) supervisors.

Holding events, evenings, discussions and intellectual games aimed at students' language learning in higher education. Organizing seminars, pedagogical readings, conferences of readers, sharing and popularizing the experience of teachers and students. Learning and achieving best practices and applying them in practice. To organize "clubs", "communities", "small science academies" that deeply study the inter-university of higher education and to attract scientists in order to develop their activities. He helps students in the course of the lesson, raises their spirit and mood, makes them interested in the topic, constantly moves around the room, monitors the work of groups, notes mistakes, checks intonation, eliminates misunderstandings, writes new words and phrases on the board, should provide handouts and use audiovisual equipment. However, it should be noted that teaching does not automatically mean learning. On the contrary, sometimes the teacher's active work during the lesson has a negative effect on the independent thinking of students.

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